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List of Abbreviations

AB	Advisory Board
AFPM	Axial Flux Permanent Magnet
AIT	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology
API	Application Programming Interface
CIM	Common Information Model
CHIL	Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CPS	Cyber-Physical System
CPES	Cyber-Physical Energy System
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DG	Distributed Generation
DTU	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet
DPSL	Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FEMM	Finite Element Method Magnetics
GUI	Graphic User Interface
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
HEDNO	Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator
ICCS	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems
JRA	Joint Research Activity
LIM	Latency Insertion Method
LV	Low Voltage
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MV	Medium Voltage
NA	Networking Activities
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens
OA	Open Access
OFFIS	Institute for Information Technology
OS	Open Source
PHIL	Power Hardware-in-the-Loop
PMU	Phasor Measurement Unit
PNDK	Power Networks Demonstration Centre
PSO	Particle Swarm Optimization
PV	Photovoltaic
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RI	Research Infrastructure
RSE	Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico
RWTH	Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen
SaaS	Simulation-as-a-Service
Smart RUE	Smart grids Research Unit of the Electrical and Computer Engineering School
SoC	State of Charge
SSO	Single Sign-On
TA	Trans-national Access
TSDB	Time Series Database
uAPI	Universal Application Programming Interface
UoS	University of Strathclyde

VA Virtual Access
WP Working Package

Executive Summary

This report describes the Virtual Access platform, a novelty introduced in the ERIGrid 2.0 project that offers Open Source Simulation-as-a-Service (SaaS) tools and Open Data services. In contrast to the Trans-national Access program, users do not need to apply for an access call and submit a research proposal to access the Virtual Access services. Instead, services are made available immediately, at no cost, and with minimal administrative overhead. The only steps to access the services are to fill out a web form and, if required, to create an account to log in. Eight partners of the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium implemented a total of 10 VA services. Their main functionalities and use cases can be applied to education, research, and industry.

During the ERIGrid 2.0 project, the usage of the Virtual Access services was monitored to estimate their impact. Web analytics metrics, user questionnaires and feedback, and the independent assessment of the ERIGrid 2.0 Advisory Board allowed to identify a total of 1,235 visits and 301 unique visitors, out of which 15% correspond to industry users, and the remaining 85% come from the academy. Moreover, almost 60% of them were from European Union countries, while the remaining 40% were from other countries, with a high participation from the United States, Latin America, and Asia. In addition, the assessment by the Advisory Board was fundamental to identifying aspects that led to several improvements to the VA infrastructures, such as enhanced descriptions and methods to track research outcomes. It was found that the Virtual Access services were used to support courses on renewable energies and power systems simulation, as well as to produce several research outcomes, including a bachelor's thesis and two conference contributions. Likewise, two user surveys allowed the project consortium to identify aspects that require further improvement, specifically related to documentation, user support, and user experience.

Finally, through the experience gained in the implementation, maintenance and improvement of the Virtual Access infrastructures, valuable lessons were collected that can serve as a reference for future efforts. Relevant technical aspects include the implementation of suitable cybersecurity mechanisms and improved means to track the usage of the services. Moreover, the impact of the Virtual Access platform can be increased through the preparation of additional support material (webinars, tutorials, etc.), targeting specific audiences like the industry.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This report presents the ERIGrid 2.0 Virtual Access (VA) service, a platform offering Open Source SaaS tools and Open Data to support education and research activities in topics related to energy, power systems, and smart grids. It presents the impact of the VA services in terms of reached users and VA infrastructure usage, as well as feedback obtained through web analytics, user feedback, and the independent assessment of the ERIGrid 2.0 Advisory Board (AB). Moreover, achievements in research and education, and the main lessons learned, are presented and analysed.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 presents an overview to the VA concept and describes the 10 services comprising the platform and its main use cases, Section 3 presents an assessment of the impact of the VA program, according to data collected via web analytics, key identified outcomes, and feedbacks obtained from the VA users. Section 4 describes the main lessons learned from the VA program. The deliverable is concluded in Section 5.

2 Virtual Access

2.1 Overview

The ERIGrid 2.0 project provides the opportunity to access virtual infrastructures for researchers worldwide. Building on the first ERIGrid project, the aim is to provide access to virtual data and services needed for research. This access is made available free of charge, offering open and freely available resources such as databases, real-time data, or simulation platforms. It aims at facilitating casual access with minimal administrative overhead compared to the more elaborate application and selection process used in the Trans-national Access (TA) exchange programme.

With the VA scheme, the project focuses on the publication of existing software projects and data sets under Open Access (OA)/Open Source (OS) to a broader audience. Moreover, the VA program seeks to supply VA access providers with the needed feedback from users and experts to improve their services. In addition, since the kick-off of the ERIGrid 2.0 project practically coincided with the start of the global Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, VA turned out to offer a viable alternative to physical lab access as worldwide travel was heavily restricted. At the same time, VA is capable of reaching out and attracting new users for upcoming lab access calls.

The European Commission (EC) defines VA as follows¹: “VA ensures free of charge access to e-infrastructure, namely to

- *Sophisticated computer services,*
- *Powerful computers, networks, grids, repositories, databases,*
- *Safely storing large quantities of scientific data,*
- *Participation in virtual research communities, and*
- *World-class operational communication and computing infrastructure to facilitate scientific research.”*

This means VA is not the same as remote laboratory (i.e., TA) access. Specifically, in the context of the ERIGrid 2.0 project, both access opportunities are provided over communication networks. However, only access to VA facilities is open to all users (i.e., users are not selected based on their research proposals). Furthermore, in the VA modality, there is no competitive selection of the users as in the lab access (remote or on-site) procedure through the TA program. The remote lab access follows the same procedure as the on-site lab access and includes individual on-site support from the access provider.

VA may require user identification or not. This can be implemented through a user login system and automated means of user verification (e.g., e-mail addresses) to avoid the abuse of services. The implementation of user identification depends on the Research Infrastructure (RI) policies of the respective access providers.

2.2 Provided Facilities and Services

This section presents the available VA services offered within the project.

¹http://www.rich2020.eu/tas_calls/about

In the ERIGrid 2.0 project, 8 out of the 20 consortium partners were offering at least one VA infrastructure. These partners were:

- AIT Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT),
- Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU),
- Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator (HEDNO),
- Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) – National Technical University of Athens (NTUA),
- Institute for Information Technology (OFFIS),
- Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico (RSE),
- Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen (RWTH), and
- University of Strathclyde (UoS).

In total, ten VA infrastructures were made available, with ICCS and AIT each providing access to two facilities. Figure 1 presents an overview of the available facilities as listed in the ERIGrid 2.0 lab access page².

Figure 1: Overview of the provided VA facilities.

Although these facilities were developed independently based on each provider's specifications and requirements of each provider, they share a common set of services that ensure authentication and access control, usage statistics collection, and user support. These services are integrated into a single workflow, as shown in Figure 2.

Once the user selects a platform, they are redirected to the VA User Questionnaire, where they can voluntarily provide information such as their e-mail address and affiliation. Next – although not shown in Figure 2 – the user may be optionally redirected to the Single Sign-On (SSO) service. After successful registration and authentication, they are granted access to the selected VA service. Further interaction with the provider can occur through the user support forum.

Unlike the TA programme, the VA users are not required to submit any results following their use of the services. However, if they choose to publish articles or reports based on their VA

²<https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access/>

Figure 2: Overview of the VA user flow.

usage, they are encouraged to acknowledge the ERIGrid 2.0 project. Additionally, users may opt to participate in the VA user survey to provide further feedback.

VA services can be broadly categorized into two types: *Simulation Tools* and *Open Data*. The following section presents the key features of each VA facility.

2.2.1 Simulation Tools

Virtual Lab of ICCS-NTUA

The Virtual Lab³ (see Figure 3) is an online educational simulation tool that mimics the operation of the actual laboratory single-phase microgrid of the EES lab of ICCS-NTUA. A mathematical model of the laboratory microgrid has been developed along with a friendly Graphic User Interface (GUI). The tool is web-based, eliminating the need to download any software and allowing multiple users to access it simultaneously. The user can access the web platform with a simple sign-up process. Once the user has logged in, they can observe several variables (e.g., voltage, active power, reactive power, etc.) and perform several actions (e.g., change the power factor of the inverter). The simulation tool includes two different laboratory setups and corresponding experiments:

- *Voltage control*: The experiment aims to demonstrate the voltage rise that can occur in distribution networks due to the high levels of Distributed Generation (DG), particularly from Photovoltaic (PV) systems. It also highlights the ancillary services provided by modern DG inverters to mitigate this issue.
- *Microgrid operation*: The main objective of this experiment is to familiarise the user with the concept of microgrids in both grid-connected and islanded operating modes.

Figure 3: Screenshot of the ICCS-NTUA Virtual Lab.

³<https://erigrd2.eu/virtual-lab/>

OpenAFPM of ICCS-NTUA

The OpenAFPM⁴ (Online Design Tools for Locally Manufactured Small Wind Turbines, see Figure 4) modelling tools can be used for designing Axial Flux Permanent Magnet (AFPM) generators for wind electric systems with the use of the open-source finite element analysis software “Finite Element Method Magnetics (FEMM).” This tool-set assists designers and practitioners involved with small-scale wind electric systems and is also used for educational purposes.

The tool MagnAFPM can be used for designing a generator for a specific set of rotor blades and a specific set of permanent magnet dimensions. The tool UserAFPM can be used to validate the performance of a specific generator geometry by performing a finite element analysis using FEMM. The tool OptiAFPM uses Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) to optimise the dimensions of the permanent magnets used in the generator design for a specific set of rotor blades, while minimising the generator’s cost and mass, and maximising its efficiency.

This VA service is tightly integrated with the educational activities of the project (i.e., Working Package (WP)04-Networking Activities (NA)3), particularly the preparation and release of a step-by-step instructional video guiding the manufacturing of small wind turbines.

OpenAFPM has been developed by the Rural Electrification Research Group (RurERG), part of the Smart grids Research Unit of the Electrical and Computer Engineering School (Smart RUE)⁵ of NTUA.

RURERG.NET
Rural Electrification Research Group

Navigation

- Design Tips
- Discussion Forum
- User Locations

User login

Username *

Password *

- Create new account
- Request new password

Log in

Sim Engine

Status: OnLine

Online Design Tools for Locally Manufactured Small Wind Turbines

The OpenAFPM modeling tools can be used for designing Axial Flux Permanent Magnet (AFPM) generators for wind electric systems with the use of the open source finite element analysis software 'Finite Element Method Magnetics' (FEMM). This series of design tools have been developed by the Rural Electrification Research Group (RurERG), which is part of the SmartRUE (Smart grids Research Unit of the Electrical and Computer Engineering School) of the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), in order to assist designers and practitioners involved with small scale wind electric systems.

The tool MagnAFPM can be used for designing a generator for a specific set of rotor blades and a specific set of permanent magnet dimensions. The tool UserAFPM can be used to validate the performance of a specific generator geometry by performing a finite element analysis using FEMM. The tool OptiAFPM uses the particle swarm optimization (PSO) to optimize the dimensions of the permanent magnets used in the generator design for a specific set of rotor blades, while minimizing the generator's cost and mass, and maximizing its efficiency.

The creation of the online user interface of the OpenAFPM modeling tools has been supported by WISIONS as part of the project 'Online Design Tools for Locally Manufactured Small Wind Turbines'

WISIONS
of sustainability

Figure 4: Screenshot of ICCS-NTUA's OpenAFPM.

⁴<https://erigid2.eu/openafpm/>

⁵<https://smartrue.gr/>

SmartEST Sim Lab of AIT

AIT's SmartEST Sim Lab⁶ (see Figure 5) is a SaaS platform that is open to the public and can be used free of charge. It provides a web-based co-simulation platform based on mosaik, Docker, JupyterLab, and JupyterHub.

The mosaik-docker JupyterLab extension, developed by AIT, integrates the package mosaik-docker into the interactive JupyterLab environment⁷. This allows to use mosaik-docker in three possible ways:

- Use JupyterLab's graphical user interface,
- Use a JupyterLab Python notebook, and
- Use a JupyterLab terminal.

This simulation platform can be used to analyse the operation of coupled thermal and electrical distribution networks and the load flow of power grids with different types of prosumers (e.g., households, electric vehicles, etc.).

An introduction to the basic workflow of the package mosaik-docker (see Figure 6) can be found in the *mosaik-docker-jl* documentation⁸.

Figure 5: Screenshot of AIT's SmartEST Sim Lab.

⁶<https://erigrid2.eu/smartest-sim-lab/>

⁷<https://github.com/ERIGrid2/mosaik-docker-jl>

⁸<https://mosaik-docker.readthedocs.io/>

Figure 6: Screenshot of mosaik-docker-jl.

SESA Virtual Sim of OFFIS

The core of the SESA Virtual Sim⁹ is formed by an online demo of the co-simulation framework mosaik. This live version of the demo scenario represents a simple but comprehensive smart grid simulation consisting of OS models. It comprises a simplistic grid (represented by PYPOWER), and households and PV panels connected to it (integrated as time series via the mosaik-householdsim and mosaik-csv adapters). It is an online simulation running in a Docker container on a server in OFFIS. The simulation is interactively visualised via mosaik-web. Each simulated model entity, namely grid buses, households, and PV modules, is represented via spheres, which are connected according to the simulation topology of the scenario. Their inner colour is changing according to the current value of each element. The user can click on the individual elements to get a moving temporal visualisation.

Three scenarios are simulated, each representing a different month – April, August, and December 2014 – corresponding to medium, high, and low PV active power levels, respectively (see Figure 7). Each month is simulated in an infinite loop. The user can switch between them via the corresponding buttons. The progress within the simulated months is shown via the blue bar at the top of the frame. If the simulation end is reached, one can refresh the browser window to restart from the beginning.

VLab of RWTH

The VLab¹⁰ of RWTH provides a web-based simulation platform (see Figure 8) integrating existing simulation tools, such as DPsim¹¹ and VILLASnode¹², for providing simulation-as-a-service to a broader audience. This platform is built upon JupyterHub, a widespread open-source tool for interactive computing. The platform provides access to RWTH's dynamic phasor solver DPsim (Mirz, Dinkelbach, & Monti, 2020), which allows building simulation scenarios for load flow, small-signal, transient and sub-transient analysis in single-phase and three-phase systems. The tool can import grids defined according to the Common Information Model (CIM) standard and includes some benchmarks such as the CIGRE-MV and the IEEE 9 bus.

⁹<https://erigrd2.eu/sesa-virtual-sim/>

¹⁰<https://erigrd2.eu/vlab/>

¹¹<https://dpsim.fein-aachen.org/>

¹²<https://www.fein-aachen.org/projects/villas-node/>

Figure 7: Screenshot of a mosaik web simulation.

Figure 8: Screenshot of RWTH's VLab.

Multi-Energy Network Simulation Benchmark of AIT

The Multi-Energy Network Simulation Benchmark¹³ provides the reference implementations of the multi-energy networks benchmark model, developed in WP-Joint Research Activity (JRA)1 (D'Arco et al., 2022), GUI for exploring the documentation and the source code, execution of simulations with the help of Jupyter notebooks, as shown in Figure 9. This benchmark runs a voltage control algorithm using a power-to-heat facility as a flexible load, integrating local Renewable Energy Sources (RES) for supporting the heat supply.

Figure 9: Screenshot of AIT's Benchmark Multi-energy Networks.

2.2.2 Open Data

DER-TF DAAS of RSE

RSE DER-TF is a real low-voltage microgrid that interconnects different generators, storage systems and loads designed and used to develop studies and experimentation on Distributed Energy Resources (DER) and Smart Grid Solutions. The facility extends over an area of about 20.000 m^2 , and it is interconnected to the Medium Voltage (MV) Grid using an 800 kVA dedicated transformer (23 kV/400 V).

RSE's DER-TF DaaS¹⁴ (see Figures 10 and 11) is a platform that provides access to historical

¹³<https://erigid2.eu/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks/>

¹⁴<https://erigid2.eu/der-tf-daas/>

Figure 10: RSE's DER-TF facility.

and real-time data of a real low-voltage microgrid. The infrastructure is composed of a Time Series Database (TSDB) and an object storage (topology, assets, test case description) that is accessible through a web interface that allows the exploration of the information at component and system levels. This infrastructure is cloud-oriented with a web application which allows simultaneous use by several users.

This platform provides free access to historical and real-time data of the RSE's DER-TF. The data are organised in several dashboards and can be displayed and downloaded considering a settable time lapse. The main data is:

- Electrical quantities (voltage, frequency, active and reactive power),
- Energy storage systems data (voltage, current, State of Charge (SoC) and power),
- Configuration of the DER-TF (breaker status),
- DC microgrid (voltage, power, SoC and status),
- PV measurement (AC and DC side, weather condition), and
- Weather and RES (PV and wind) production forecast.

Smartgrid MVP of UoS

Smartgrid MVP¹⁵, shown in Figure 12, is developed by the Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (DPSL) (Hong et al., 2019). It collects power system measurement data from multiple data sources, including the Phasor Measurement Unit (PMU), within a single platform. This allows the data to be shared with other interested parties in real-time (or near-real-time). Furthermore, historical recorded data (e.g., within a certain time range) will be available to access and download. Optionally, an analysis can be performed locally on the data, such as the correlation with other power system events and data sources.

¹⁵<https://erigrd2.eu/smartgrid-mvp/>

Figure 11: Screenshot of RSE's DER-TF DaaS PV field production.

Two PMUs have been installed onto the electrical networks at the UoS and the Power Networks Demonstration Centre (PNDC) for this project. Currently, no GB-focused online monitoring platforms display PMU data, whereas the Smart Grid Monitoring and Visualisation Platform (SGMVP) has been developed to display PMU data alongside operational network data in real-time. PMU data is not readily available in the public domain, so this source benefits future academic research, network operators and other interested parties.

SGRID of HEDNO

SGRID¹⁶ is a web interface, accessible 24/7, that provides live metering data from the Greek distribution system. In its current configuration, it provides the collective renewable and thermal energy production for the Greek island of Milos (see Figure 13). The data is provided with a delay of a couple of hours and with a sample rate of 15 minutes. Both live and historical data are available for visualisation and download.

HEDNO collects telemetering data from a wide range of MV and Low Voltage (LV) producers (thermal and RES) and consumers throughout Greece from smart meters. These metering data are available through a web-based application that allows customers to check their electricity consumption and generation. The MV customers can access their metering data through a

¹⁶<https://erigrd2.eu/sgrid/>

Figure 12: Screenshot of UoS’s Smartgrid MVP.

web platform. However, specific metering data per customer cannot be made public due to the relevant personal data legislation, and researchers cannot be granted access to this platform. HEDNO, therefore, for the needs of ERIGrid 2.0, proposed the anonymous provision of such metering data to the scientific community. To realise this target, telemetry data from producers in microgrids have been grouped per production type (i.e., thermal, wind, and solar). Greek islands are most often not interconnected to the main system and thus constitute microgrids that have multiple thermal, wind, and solar production sites. The sum of the production of multiple producers of the same type provides the necessary personal data security. The scientific

Figure 13: Screenshot of HEDNO’s SGRID.

community is, therefore, given a new web interface that includes only the relevant summed data (available for viewing and download) per 15 minutes for a complete microgrid system.

SYSLAB VA of DTU

SYSLAB VA¹⁷ provides a database containing real-time and historical data streamed from the SYSLAB laboratory. Datasets include meteorological data, renewable energy production, network measurements, and smart building sensor data (see Figure 14). The SYSLAB laboratory consists of electrical and district heating distribution grids with controllable energy system units. The infrastructure has been specifically designed for testing distributed control architectures and features a high degree of automation, with almost the entire laboratory being remotely controllable through an Application Programming Interface (API).

Data from about 2,500 measurement points across the laboratory are continuously collected at a 1-second interval. The virtual access facility provides a subset of these data, both real-time and historical, at 5-second resolution from various devices and sensors. Parallel to an ongoing extension of the SYSLAB facility during 2022, it was planned to continuously expand the scope of the VA with additional datasets during the remainder of the project.

Figure 14: Screenshot of DTU's SYSLAB VA.

¹⁷<https://erigrd2.eu/syslab-va/>

2.3 Use Cases

This section describes the main use cases that can be covered by the VA services.

2.3.1 Education

The initiative of offering simulation tools and related resources as VA services started in ERIGrid as part of the education and training WP. Platforms providing different experiments were offered via web interfaces and Jupyter Notebooks (Strasser et al., 2020). The success of these initiatives led to the VA access in ERIGrid 2.0, where these resources were enhanced and extended with contributions and OS tools offered by more project partners.

Many of these platforms can be used for educational purposes and give users flexibility for implementing their experiments. Both platforms offered by ICCS, Virtual Lab and OpenAFPM, are focused on education and include useful documentation and other material such as videos. Their focus is on teaching fundamentals of inverter-based generation and renewable energies. Moreover, the Vlab offered by RWTH includes several examples to illustrate key concepts of power system simulation, such as Modified Nodal Analysis, Resistive Companion, Dynamic Phasors, and more advanced topics like Diakoptics (Mirz, 2020).

2.3.2 Research Activities

The inclusion of Open Data and SaaS tools with which scenarios of different levels of sophistication and complexity can be achieved, makes the VA services ideal for research activities. Open data corresponding to living labs (SYSLAB VA), microgrids (DER-TF DaaS), DSO (SGRID), and a national power system (SmartGrid MVP), which users can download as Comma-Separated Values (CSV) files, can support a wide range of power system research applications.

Moreover, tools for power system simulation (Vlab), co-simulation (SESA Virtual Sim, SmartEST Sim Lab) and the multi-energy networks benchmark are a result of multiple research efforts, and their underlying methods have been published (Mirz et al., 2020; Ofenloch et al., 2022; Widl, Wild, Heussen, Rikos, & Hoang, 2022). In this way, these VA infrastructures can constitute a starting point for interested researchers.

2.3.3 Industry

The flexibility of mosaik and DPsim, as the core simulation tools of the SmartEST Sim Lab and Vlab, respectively, allows for building relevant scenarios for the industry. First, both tools allow co-simulation, and as a consequence, the implementation of complex Cyber-Physical System (CPS). In addition, the high interoperability of DPsim allows for building and testing more realistic power system applications.

Both VA services can be used in the early stages of a more complex Cyber-Physical Energy System (CPES) testing workflow, such as the one proposed in ERIGrid (Heussen et al., 2019). The validated simulation scenarios can later be used in Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop (CHIL) and Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL) experimental setups to test power and control devices.

3 Impact of the Virtual Access Program

This section presents the impact of the VA services, according to user data collected directly through online forms, surveys, and indirectly through web analytics tools. Moreover, the services were assessed independently by the project's AB three times during its lifetime.

Early after their deployment, VA services were promoted in a joint webinar together with DER-lab and the PANTERA project, namely "Remote Testing and EIRIE Platform"¹⁸. A total of 96 attendees participated, where a description of the platform and two demos were presented. In addition, the VA services were presented as part of the "First Webinar of RICH Europe on Transnational and Virtual Access Opportunities (TA/VA)"¹⁹ in November of 2022.

3.1 User Reach and Engagement

Some VA services were already available from the ERIGrid project. This resulted in some usage statistics being collected from the beginning of ERIGrid 2.0. During the first year, more ancillary services were implemented to have more accurate estimations of the VA services usage, including the user questionnaire, which is a web form through which users can voluntarily provide minimal information such as name, e-mail address, country, and affiliation. This tool was useful in identifying users who were not simply browsing the project's web page, but were using the VA services. The inclusion of the questionnaire as part of the VA platform was made in August 2020, during the times of the COVID-19 pandemic. Despite these difficult times, the impact of the VA services was remarkable from the beginning.

Users started to participate in the first 18 months, increased substantially in the second 18-month period, and continued to use the services constantly until the end of the project. From the total number of unique visitors to the ERIGrid 2.0 lab access page, the consortium estimates that around 8% of them accessed the VA services. A total of 1,213 unique visits to the VA platforms were registered via the user questionnaire, as shown in Figure 15. From these visits, around 15% were from the industry, while the remaining 85% came from academic institutions. Furthermore, unique users were filtered out, resulting in an estimated number of 301. Here, unique users are taken as those who can be linked to a unique email account. As users can decide not to fill out the user questionnaire, this number can be taken as a lower bound.

In terms of geographical coverage, visitors from all over the world were reached, with significant participation from North and South America, as well as Asia (see Figure 16). European countries represent almost 60% of the number of visits, as shown in Figure 17.

The user surveys, carried out in 2022 and 2024, allowed the consortium to know more about the VA users. The majority are employees from the academic sector or the industry, with diverse career levels including graduate and PhD students, postdoctoral researchers and professors. In addition, users indicated the frequency with which they used the services.

3.2 Main Outcomes

This section presents the main outcomes of the VA program in terms of education and research activities.

¹⁸ <https://der-lab.net/remote-testing-eirie-platform-webinar-on-demand/>

¹⁹ <https://rich-europe.eu/transnational-virtual-access-opportunities-23rd-november-2022-video-recording-and-materials/>

Figure 15: Accumulated number of visits to the VA services.

Figure 16: Origins of users based on their IP address, data gathered from August 2020 to March 2025.

3.2.1 Education

Three VA services were used to support educational activities and events. They are described as follows:

- As already mentioned in Section 2.2.1, ICCS' OpenAFPM released a video²⁰ entitled "How to Build a Small Wind Turbine." The tools featured by this VA platform can be used to support the design process. The video became the most popular on the ERIGrid 2.0 YouTube channel, with more than 20k views.
- The Virtual Lab of ICCS is part of a course offered at NTUA on distributed generation and renewable energies. Several lab exercises enabled by Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL)

²⁰<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YImH3HXVn54>

Figure 17: Origins of users within the EU based on their IP address, data gathered from August 2020 to March 2025.

illustrate principles related to voltage control and microgrid operation. A broader audience could be reached beyond the physical lab through the Virtual Lab, which, as described in Section 2.2.1, implements a simulation model of the actual laboratory microgrid.

- The Vlab at RWTH is regularly used for education, particularly as a support tool for courses on power system dynamics and simulation. Initially, the Vlab incorporated the lecture examples and exercises from the course “Modeling and Simulation of Complex Power Systems” with topics such as Resistive Companion, Diakoptics and the Latency Insertion Method (LIM)²¹. In addition, the Vlab platform includes more than 50 examples as Jupyter Notebooks ranging from component model testing and comparison, to EMT simulation of benchmark systems including the IEEE 9 bus and the CIGRE MV grid.

3.2.2 Research Activities

Although it is more difficult to track how the VA services are used for research activities, as compared to the TA program, we could gather three relevant research outcomes through the second user survey of 2024, which are listed as follows:

- BSc dissertation in the topic of axial flux generators for locally manufactured small wind turbines, which used the VA service OpenAFPM of ICCS-NTUA.
- Conference paper entitled “Measurement-based harmonic analysis of electric vehicle smart charging” (Senol et al., 2024), in which the infrastructure and open data platform SYSLAB VA of DTU was used. The users mentioned that there is an associated journal paper under review.

²¹ <https://www.acs.eonerc.rwth-aachen.de/cms/E-ON-ERC-ACS/Studium/Lehrveranstaltungen/~dscl/Modeling-and-Simulation-of-Complex-Power/lidx/1/>

- Contribution to the E-WAV International Conference on Energy, Water, Advancements, and Visions²².

3.3 User Feedback

User feedback was collected from user surveys carried out in 2022 and 2024. These surveys included questions to rate several aspects of the VA services, indicate the preferred form of support, and also to provide comments and additional feedback.

Tables 1 and 2 show how the users who participated in both surveys rated some aspects of the VA services in the surveys of 2022 and 2024, respectively.

Table 1: Scores of the survey participants related to the VA services in the user survey of 2022.

Question	1	2	3	4	5	No Answer
The service was useful for my work/research	1	0	1	5	7	11
The service was interesting	1	0	0	3	11	10
The service was properly documented	0	2	2	6	4	11
The service was easy to use	0	2	1	5	7	10
I would recommend the service to somebody else	1	0	1	6	7	10
Data can be exported in format which is compatible with my workflow	0	1	2	4	6	12

Table 2: Scores of the survey participants related to the VA services in the user survey of 2024.

Question	1	2	3	4	5	No Answer
The service was useful for my work/research	0	0	0	2	3	14
The service was interesting	0	0	1	1	3	14
The service was properly documented	0	0	2	1	2	14
The service was easy to use	0	0	2	1	2	14
I would recommend the service to somebody else	0	0	0	2	4	13
Data can be exported in format which is compatible with my workflow	0	0	1	4	3	14

Feedback in most aspects was positive. It was also important to understand that some aspects, like documentation, ease of use, and data exporting, need to be improved. This was also confirmed in the comments that some survey participants freely provided.

To provide users with a tool for getting support, it was agreed in ERIGrid 2.0 to implement a user forum, through which users can submit questions or inform about issues, and get answers from the VA service administrators. In this regard, the user survey included a question asking if they used the forum. Only 19% indicated that they used it. In agreement with the question asking which type of support was preferred by them, the majority specified approaches like written documentation, tutorial videos, and example models or data. Very few of them specified forums or mailing lists.

²²<https://sites.google.com/view/ewav2024/>

3.4 Independent Assessment by Advisory Board

An independent assessment of the VA services was made by the ERIGrid 2.0 AB, composed of highly reputed representatives from the academic sector and industry. This assessment became an important interaction and feedback channel through which some improvements were identified and implemented.

Overall, the AB agreed upon positive aspects of the VA services, some of which are listed as follows:

- The fact that they constitute a novel and innovative approach to extend the audience and impact of European RIs.
- Their relevance and usefulness in the context of the energy transition towards a Smart Grid.
- The reason is that they promote open science, OS, and Open Data as key components enabling research in the energy field.
- Their high level of usage and availability.

Likewise, some aspects that require further improvement were identified by the AB. These included enhanced descriptions and documentation of the VA services, particularly in terms of their service capabilities and use cases, as well as their relationship with other project activities like the JRAs and TAs. Other aspects included the need for more promotion efforts such as webinars and tutorials, an improved user experience, and efforts to increase industry participation.

4 Lessons Learned

Throughout the project, valuable insights were gained across multiple dimensions of the Virtual Access (VA) activities. These lessons reflect both the challenges encountered and the opportunities identified while designing, deploying, and operating the services. They also highlight areas where user expectations, technical feasibility, and organisational processes intersect. The following subsections summarise key findings related to the infrastructure and tools, user engagement, industry involvement, and collaboration with other WPs.

4.1 Virtual Access Infrastructures and Tools

The development and deployment of VA services have revealed several important lessons regarding the underlying infrastructures and tools. One key technical challenge has been *ensuring secure operation and service integration* in a distributed environment, particularly regarding cybersecurity and the integration of the VA infrastructures with external services via API. Regarding cybersecurity, when containerising the services for their deployment, it is critical to apply access restrictions to avoid platform misuse. This was experienced by one of the VA infrastructures. The issue becomes more relevant if the infrastructure gives high flexibility to the user, e.g. the use of terminals and the execution of arbitrary code, such as that based on Jupyter Notebooks.

Regarding the platform integration aspects, it is clear that the use cases of the VA services can be substantially increased with the use of APIs, for instance, a continuous stream of measurements from an Open Data service into a local Digital Twin, or a co-simulation or Software-in-the-Loop with one of the SaaS providers. Tools to simplify this integration were implemented and tested in the project, including an OpenAPI specification for distributed HIL and co-simulation experiments, namely the Universal Application Programming Interface (uAPI). Moreover, its use for getting simulation data was successfully demonstrated in one of the ERIGrid 2.0 Massive Open Online Course (MOOC), as part of the WP4-NA3 related to education and training.

An example of such a setup is presented in Figure 18, where a user implements a state estimation locally and communicates with the simulator provided by the VA service via uAPI. The user implements a client version of this API. Although some extra effort is required to enable the communication modules from the VA infrastructure side, taking special care of the cybersecurity part, the fact that it has already been tested in one of the MOOCs demonstrates the feasibility of this scenario.

Another relevant aspect concerns *usage monitoring*. Identifying unique users and distinguishing between one-time and frequent users is technically complex but also essential for assessing the impact of the services and for guiding future improvements. Establishing more systematic methods for collecting and analysing user interaction data is crucial to the refinement of the VA platform. Some tasks that contribute to this aspect are identified as follows:

- *Careful monitoring and continuous assessment of the web analytics tools:* Due to the inherent distributed operation of the platform, through which users are redirected from the ERIGrid 2.0 main page to the local VA services, there is a risk of interrupting the collection of web analytics data every time an upgrade of the local service takes place. Having additional tools to monitor and test data collection can mitigate this risk.
- *Continuous optimisation of the web analytics tool:* Web Analytics tools are continuously evolving and offering more advanced functionalities. Tuning these tools to focus more on

Figure 18: Example use case of VA service integration with a local service provided by the user.

the usage of the VA services and the estimation of unique and frequent users will not only give improved estimates of the impact and evolution of the platform, but also provide hints on how to improve the services and user experience.

- *Implementation of more attractive user surveys:* In the two user surveys carried out during the operation of the VA services, it was difficult to encourage users to participate and complete them. Today, it is a general problem that is addressed by offering participants some form of reward. A better understanding of this aspect in the context of the VA services, through which more compact and attractive surveys can be implemented, would improve the collection of usage data and feedback.
- *Improvement of user forms:* The user questionnaire proved to be an effective tool to gather usage data and get minimal information about the user. It was used to get a more accurate estimation of the number of unique users and visits. During the operation of the VA services, it was verified that a clearer workflow for this tool would have been better, for example, requiring the user to decide if they want to fill the user form or not. Moreover, a more rigorous process of validation of form fields would have facilitated the automated collection of usage statistics.

4.2 Interaction with Users

Effective user engagement is essential to maintain the high impact of the VA services. Feedback collected throughout the project indicates a need for more accessible and comprehensive support materials. Specifically, users have expressed interest in additional video tutorials and improved documentation to facilitate onboarding and self-guided learning. Clear, step-by-step guides and annotated examples were particularly valued by users with limited prior experience in simulation tools or data platforms.

In addition, the organisation of interactive events, such as webinars, has proven valuable in raising awareness, demonstrating functionalities, and gathering feedback. Increasing the frequency and variety of such events could significantly enhance user support and community building. These events not only serve as training opportunities but also foster a sense of community among users, encouraging knowledge exchange and peer support.

To further strengthen engagement, the integration of feedback mechanisms directly within the

VA platforms, such as embedded surveys, quick feedback buttons, or user satisfaction prompts, could provide real-time insights into user needs. Moreover, establishing a structured onboarding process, including welcome emails, introductory walkthroughs, and curated learning paths, would help new users navigate the services more effectively.

A moderated discussion forum was also provided²³, offering a dedicated space for users to ask questions, report issues, and exchange ideas. While usage of the forum was limited during the project, it remains a valuable channel for asynchronous support and community interaction. Promoting this forum more actively and integrating it more visibly into the VA user flow could help increase its adoption and effectiveness.

Finally, the creation of a broader user community space, complementing the forum with features such as topic tagging, expert questions and answer sessions, and user showcases, could further facilitate ongoing dialogue between users and service providers. This would allow users to share experiences, suggest improvements, and contribute to the continuous evolution of the VA services.

4.3 Industry Involvement and Related Use Cases

The involvement of industry partners has shown potential but remains an area for further development. While approximately 15% of VA users identified as coming from industry, concrete use cases that clearly demonstrate the added value of VA services for industrial stakeholders are still limited. This suggests that while awareness exists, deeper engagement and integration into industrial workflows have yet to be fully realised.

Collaborative activities that align technical offerings with practical industrial needs should be prioritised to increase adoption and sustained usage. For example, simulation tools such as mosaik and DPsim offer capabilities that could support early-stage prototyping, system validation, or training within industrial research and development departments. However, these opportunities require clearer communication of benefits, tailored documentation, and potentially co-developed demonstration cases that reflect real-world industrial challenges.

To support this, future VA initiatives could include targeted outreach to industry associations, participation in sector-specific events, and the development of industry-focused webinars or tutorials. Additionally, establishing feedback loops with industrial users—through surveys, interviews, or pilot collaborations—would help identify barriers to adoption and inform the evolution of the services.

The continuation of VA services by AIT and RWTH in the successor project RISEnergy²⁴ presents a valuable opportunity to deepen industry engagement. By building on the technical maturity and visibility of these platforms, RISEnergy can serve as a bridge to more robust industrial use cases, fostering long-term collaboration between RIs and the private sector.

4.4 Collaboration with Trans-national Access and Joint Research

Stronger synergies between the VA program and other project activities, such as the TA and JRA, have been identified as a strategic opportunity. In particular, using VA services as an entry point or promotional tool to attract potential TA users could enhance the reach and impact

²³<https://forum.erigrd2.eu/>

²⁴<https://risenergy-project.eu/va-access/>

of both programs. The low-barrier, on-demand nature of VA allows users to explore tools and datasets before committing to more resource-intensive TA engagements, thereby serving as a natural onboarding mechanism.

Additionally, linking demos and developments from WPJRA4 more explicitly to VA services would foster integration and highlight the research-to-application process. For example, simulation models, co-simulation frameworks, or control algorithms developed in the context of joint research could be made available through VA platforms, enabling broader testing, validation, and reuse by the community.

This alignment would also contribute to a more coherent project ecosystem, facilitating broader dissemination and adoption of the results. It would allow users to follow a seamless pathway from initial exploration via VA, to deeper experimentation through TA, and finally to collaborative innovation via JRA. Establishing such a continuum would not only increase the visibility and utility of project outputs but also strengthen the long-term sustainability of the RI network.

Looking ahead, the continuation of selected VA services in the RISEnergy project offers a concrete opportunity to implement and refine these synergies. By building on the foundations laid in ERIGrid 2.0, future initiatives can further integrate access modalities and research activities to support a more dynamic and user-driven innovation environment.

5 Conclusions

The ERIGrid 2.0's VA platform has successfully demonstrated the potential of open, on-demand digital infrastructures to support education, research, and industry in the evolving landscape of smart energy systems. By offering a suite of OS simulation tools and Open Data services, the VA initiative has significantly broadened the reach and impact of European RIs, particularly during a time when physical access was constrained due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

During the project's lifetime, the VA services attracted several thousand visits and hundreds of unique users. The services reached a global audience, with the majority of users based in Europe and the remainder from North America, Latin America, and Asia. These figures, validated through web analytics and user questionnaires, underscore the platform's international relevance and accessibility.

In education, the VA services supported university courses and online learning. A notable example includes a widely viewed instructional video on wind turbine design, which complemented the OpenAFPM tool and demonstrated the platform's value in hands-on learning environments.

Feedback from user surveys and the AB highlighted the strengths of the platform—its openness, ease of access, and technical relevance—while also identifying areas for improvement. These include enhancing documentation, improving user experience, and expanding support materials such as tutorials and webinars. Notably, the AB emphasized the strategic value of VA as a complementary entry point to the TA.

Key lessons learned include the importance of robust cybersecurity and API integration for scalable, secure service delivery. Additionally, better tools are needed to monitor user engagement and track research outcomes. A user-centric design approach—featuring intuitive onboarding, clear documentation, and responsive support—was also found to be essential for maximizing impact.

In conclusion, the ERIGrid 2.0 VA initiative has not only met but exceeded its original objectives, offering a scalable and replicable model for VA in the power and energy systems domain. Its continued evolution and adoption will be essential to supporting the digital transformation of energy research and education across Europe and beyond. Notably, the VA services developed by AIT and RWTH will continue to be used and further developed in the successor project RISEnergy, ensuring continuity and long-term impact.

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